

**CHAPTER ONE
INTRODUCTION**

1.1. Background of the Study

Biodiversity dwells in the part of this planet (earth) called the biosphere. The word 'biosphere' is gotten from the Greek word 'bios' and 'spaira' which means life and sphere respectively. It is the layer of the planet earth where life exists. It is referred to as the living part of the earth where biodiversity is found. Biodiversity found on earth today consists of many millions of distinct biological species, the product of four billion years of evolution which has recorded different events of extinction. This led to the mass drop in biodiversity after many years of recovery. However, the word biodiversity is relatively new, and was first coined as a contraction of the term 'biological diversity' (which was first used by J. Authur Harris in 'The Variable Desert') in 1985 by W. G. Rosen and now popularized by a number of authors.

According to UNEP (2010), "biodiversity is the variety of life on earth. It includes all organisms, species and populations, the genetic variation among them, and their complex body of communities and ecosystem." It refers to the interrelation of genes, species and ecosystem and in turn, their interaction with the immediate environment they find themselves. Oribhabor (2016) defines biodiversity as the term used to describe the totality of different living organisms such as plants, animals (both lower and higher animals –humans), fungi and microbes that exist on the planet earth. He also said it is the total amount of species, genes and ecosystem in a geographical region. The United Nation Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2010) considers human as an integral and vital part of the earth's biodiversity. In ancient times, human species were treated separately from the rest of nature. But it was agreed that the human race is also a vital part of the earth's biodiversity.

According to the Nigeria Fifth National Biodiversity Report (NFNBR, 2015), the biodiversity of Nigeria constitutes the sources of food, raw material, wide range of goods and services and genetic materials for agriculture, medicine and health care support (under the flora family), domestic and commercial products, aesthetics and cultural values. The above-mentioned elements also constitute the value of biodiversity

to the Nigerian people. Biodiversity encompasses every living thing on earth; both those that are mobile and immobile to the physical eye.

Biodiversity in our environment is classified into three levels which are the genetic diversity, species diversity and the ecosystem diversity. The genetic diversity is the different genetic materials inherent in all living species (plants, animals, microorganisms, fungi as well as the human species). The species are the differences within and between the biological species. The ecosystem diversity comprises of the various habitat, communities, ecological system as well as the variety within individual ecosystems. (UNEP, 2010). Biodiversity on this planet is very important as it is a major contributor to the maintenance, sustenance and continual existence of the earth. This is applicable in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers state, Nigeria; which is also part of the earth and is well endowed with an ecosystem that habits biodiversity of humans, flora and fauna of different species in different habitats. It is evident that ONELGA is abundant in biodiversity of all sorts.

The term 'ecological hazard' is often interchanged with environmental hazards, challenges, problems, calamities etc. Ecological hazard is anything from the interaction with other living things, the immediate environment, or the interaction between living organisms and their immediate surrounding that poses danger or harm to biodiversity in that environment. According to Jay Scott (2011) in Ibimilua & Ibimilua (2014), environmental challenges are the occurrences that are perilous or potentially threatening to man and his immediate environment. It can also be described as any predicament that exceeds the ability of individuals, communities or a society to manage or survive its repercussion (Wright & Boorse, 2011; Mahatma, 2009; Enger and Smith, 2010; Hyde & Revee, 2011; and Mary,1995).

Furthermore, environmental challenge can be said to be an unwanted occurrence as a result of natural and human factors (or the combination of both) that has an adverse effect on the daily lives of humans, flora and fauna. Petters (1995) defined ecological hazard as any form of risk, predicament or peril resulting to loss in the environment. Chan (2005) stated that human kind as well as other biological species in this planet are currently facing serious global environmental challenges of different sorts including shortage of clean and accessible fresh water, ecosystem degradation, soil erosion, climate change and biodiversity loss. These environmental problems are interconnected and inter-related.

GWASCSA (2017) defined ecological hazards as possible sources of predicaments to man's life, health, income and property; and may have impact on elements of biophysical, managed and constructed elements of the environment. Ecological hazard is any single or collaboration of harmful toxic chemical, biological or physical substitute in our immediate environment as a result of man's interference with the environment or natural occurrence which may affect the health of subjects negatively exposed to it. These include pollutants such as heavy metals, insecticides, pesticides, biological contaminants, toxic wastes, home and industrial chemicals etc.

The causes of ecological hazards are divided into two main categories. They are astronomical (natural); and anthropogenic (human) causes. Astronomical causes of ecological hazards are those that occur naturally. Coentades (2009), in Ibimilua & Ibimilua (2014), identified the major causes of natural factors of ecological hazards as geological events, meteorological incidents as well as biological factors. Geological events are triggered by the inherent exertion of the planets; while meteorological events are caused by the differences in global weather patterns. The biological events are as a result of the actions of living organisms. In the same vein, Petters (1995) submitted that while some naturally occurring disasters (e.g. volcanic eruption, storms, earthquakes) are from the earth's intrinsic imbalance; others such as mudflow, landslides, and floods emit from the large reorganization of the earth's materials. Wright & Boorse (2011) also identified the causes of natural hazards under the categories of hydrological, meteorological and geological forces.

Anthropogenic causes are those hazards caused mainly by the interference of humans with the environment and its resources. Human activities like agriculture, fishing, livestock rearing, hunting etc. mount daily pressures on the environment. Other activities such as burning of fossil fuels, bush burning, deforestation, overgrazing, overfishing as well as the irrational use of pesticides, insecticides and herbicides are responsible for various ecological hazards. Also, the rapid growth in the world's population has resulted in the increased demands of food, clean water, energy etc. This has caused over dependence and reliance on natural resources in the environment. The absence of substitutes to which to turn to in times of needs by the population has resulted in the high level of usage of these natural resources. This has also demeaned the very sources on which man's sustenance depends (Madu, 2007). Cases of road construction, timber harvesting, uncontrolled poaching and other human activities have

resulted in the damage of dwelling places. They have also resulted in the destruction of biodiversity, especially mass species of fauna and flora. Other careless attitudes of human activities that negatively impact of biodiversity conservation include industrialization, indiscriminate use of commercial fertilizers as wells as haphazard construction of buildings and roads with no respect for urban and regional planning laws and regulations

Also, increased concentration of Green House Gases (GHGs) in our atmosphere today has become a problem leading to climate change. Green House Gases are gaseous compounds that are capable of trapping heat in the atmosphere, keeping the earth's surface warmer than it would have been if they were not present. These compounds are majorly and subsequently sourced out from the burning of fossil fuels and burning of bushes, deforestation etc. These Green House Gases (GHGs) are carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), Nitro-oxide (N₂O), Carbon Monoxide (CO), and Chlorofluorocarbon (CFCs) (Cunningham, 2009). The major causes of ecological hazards in Nigeria, and particular ONELGA are anthropogenic forces.

Ecological hazards' impacts and consequences are multi-dimensional. They vary from place to place, and from time to time. Freeman et al (2003), in Ibimilua & Ibimilua (2014) submitted that ecological hazards can have negative impacts on man and his immediate environment. In ONELGA, the consequences of ecological hazards are biodiversity loss of all species, loss of life and properties, degraded fresh water, land degradation, flooding, soil erosion etc. These consequences affect man, properties, flora, fauna and other vital components of the environment. Other outcomes are disease outbreak, stratospheric ozone layer depletion, climate change and hydrological upset. The acuteness of environmental problems in Nigeria has been documented by scholars like Petters (1995) and Franca (2002). They reported that the impacts of ecological problems include damage to the infrastructure, loss of life, injury, loss of housing, loss of crops, breakdown of social order, disruption of communication as well as disease outbreak. This is also applicable in ONELGA. This area with its well-endowed ecosystem which constitutes biological diversity of plant, agricultural trees, species of fishes and animals could experience loss (Ozor, 2009). In ONELGA, the effect of ecological hazard can be viewed from various aspects. Ecological hazard affects the biodiversity of plants and animals including aquatic animal of the ecosystem in ONELGA, causing extinction and killing of aquatic species. It is evident that ONELGA is likely going to suffer the impact of ecological hazards. This is because of the various

human activities in different regions of the Local Government Area. Also, because of its geographical location, low income and low institutional resources.

Mitigation and adaptation of ecological hazard is very necessary. Addressing these challenges will help to achieve environmental sustainability in ONELGA, and this requires the collaborative efforts of the government at all levels, NGOs, community-based organizations as well as individuals. It is important to note that ecological hazard control process is concerned with recognizing, evaluating and mitigating these perils that occur as a result of human errors and natural deficiencies in the environment (Ibimilua and Ibimilua, 2014). Natural events cannot be prevented but their impacts can be reduced by sound environmental education, disaster forecasting and mitigation, re-introduction of species, geographical remote sensing techniques and information systems.

The mitigation of anthropogenic causes of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation is based on types, causes and consequences. Generally, poverty alleviation, control of population growth, good agricultural practices without compromising the natural ecosystem, afforestation and re-afforestation programmes, channelization and regular cleaning of drainage channels to mitigate human induced flooding will help as mitigation strategies according to scholars. They also noted that effective environmental sanitation, cover-cropping, contour ploughing to control soil erosion etc. will ensure biodiversity conservation. Mitigation processes can also be carried out through scientific assessments, risk analysis, public education and involvements, political action and long-term evaluation (Raven et al, 2010).

Therefore, this research is aimed at examining the impacts of ecological hazards biodiversity conservation in ONELGA. This is to ensure proper mitigation and adaptation of the challenges posed by ecological hazards on biological species. It is also to reduce the impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation through proper education and support of the indigenes of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

Biological species are very important constituents of the biosphere in this planet. Biodiversity on earth today widely consist of many millions of distinct biological species. It is the product of approximately four billion years of evolution. Biodiversity

has recorded different events of extinction which led to the mass drop, and many years of recovery. Biodiversity is of a very great importance on earth, as it plays an important role in the maintenance, sustenance and continual existence of the earth's biosphere. This is also applicable in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area. The human species, flora and fauna of different species (biodiversity) are functional in the earth's ecosystem. The care, conservation and maintenance of biological diversity is also very important to avoid further extinction and drop especially in ONELGA. It is pertinent, therefore, to look into the various biological species, and conserve them against possible extinction.

Ecological hazard is the negative changes in the normal setting of the ecosystem as a result of harmful and dangerous substances, states or activities introduced into the natural environment. It has long been one of the major threats to biological diversity. They are either chemical, physical, biological or psycho-social hazards threatening the existence of biodiversity. Issues of fresh water degradation, oil pollution, gas flaring, soil erosion, desertification, habitat degradation of various species, flooding, climate and animal epidemic affect biodiversity conservation. Also, diseases, pest invasions, destructive storms caused by astronomical (natural) and anthropogenic (human interference) factors affect biodiversity. Therefore, studying the nature and causes of these hazards becomes pertinent. These hazards also impact negatively on the biological diversity of ONELGA.

In recent times, biological species have become targets of human needs due to the blooming human population and the hunt for a 'better life' through the improvement of today's science and technology. Unfortunately, biological species are being misused at a much higher and faster rates than ever in ancient times with adverse effects for a better human livelihood. Biodiversity is facing a major crisis of grave proportion. This could ultimately lead to mass extinction of biological species in the very near future. Therefore, the importance of conserving biodiversity cannot be overemphasized, and let efforts have been made in this regard in ONELGA.

The impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity are complex and multidimensional. These consequences differ in kinds, places and times. In ONELGA, the consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity include loss of all species with different habitations, fresh water degradation, loss of life and properties, flooding, soil erosion, human and animal diseases outbreaks. Others include climate change, destruction of

farmlands, habitat degradation, extinction of various biological species of flora and fauna etc. These hazardous activities are really detrimental to biological species' conservation. This necessitated the need to examine the various impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity in ONELGA.

The need to address and proffer solutions to the adverse effects of ecological hazards on biodiversity in ONELGA cannot be overemphasized. It is the duty of governments, Non-government Organizations, community-based organizations, as well as individuals to tackle and address the challenges of ecological hazards. Proper and sound environmental education, environmental monitoring and sanitation, poverty alleviation, control of population growth, management of waste and treatment etc. have been put forward by scholars as ways to conserve biodiversity. Also, channelization and regular cleaning of drainage channels, cover-cropping, afforestation, re-introduction of species have also been identified as mitigation strategies against biodiversity losses. This research will also look into the different solutions available and see how they can be utilized in addressing the challenges posed by ecological hazards on biological species in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers state.

The ability of governments, Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs), Multi-national Corporations (MNCs) and Community Based Organizations (CBSs) to mitigate the challenges posed by ecological hazards is dependent on the level of knowledge, quality of information available to them by environmental educators and campaigners, and the willingness to act. Human species who are the outstanding biological diversity (higher fauna) and sole attributors of hazards in the environment (anthropogenic factors) should be enlightened on the causes of ecological hazards, its consequences on them, as well as other biological species in the environment and the natural resources in the environment. They should also be educated on how to tackle the problems facing them through mitigation and adaptation strategies or measures. This is to ensure that their daily interactions with the natural environment are sustainable and profitable. These scholastic solutions and strategies proffered in addressing the challenges of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation have not been adequately applied in ONELGA.

Therefore, the research seeks to critically examine the nature, causes, impacts and challenges of ecological hazards on biological species' conservation in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, and proffer solutions on its mitigation and adaptation strategies.

1.3. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this research was to ascertain the impact of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the nature and types of biodiversity in ONELGA;
2. Determine the causes of biodiversity loss in ONELGA;
3. Highlight the impacts and/or consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity in ONELGA;
4. Make suggestions on how to conserve biodiversity in ONELGA.

1.4. Research Questions

This research was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the nature and types of biodiversity in ONELGA?
- ii. What are the causes of biodiversity loss in ONELGA?
- iii. What are the impacts and/or consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity in ONELGA?
- iv. What are the ways to conserve biodiversity in ONELGA?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis will be used in this research:

- i. Ecological hazards have not significantly altered the nature of biodiversity in ONELGA
- ii. Ecological hazards have not impacted significantly on biodiversity depletion in ONELGA.

1.6. Scope of the Study

This study focuses on the impact of ecological hazard on biodiversity in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. This work is therefore limited to the comprehensive and critical examination of the nature, impacts and challenges of biodiversity conservation in ONELGA. Solutions will also be proffered through recommendations in order to provide the people of the local government and indeed the Nigerian state, strategies for mitigation and adaptation for biodiversity conservation.

1.7. Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be helpful and useful to individuals, researchers, students, governments and Non-governmental Organizations.

- i. **Individuals:** Individuals will be using the findings of this study to adequately take care of the natural resources in their environment. It will help individuals understand the reasons why the environment today is becoming harmful to various biological species in the ecosystem. It will also help individuals to understand various ways they can tackle the issues of ecological hazards and also reveal and enlighten them on ways to safeguard the natural resources and the immediate environment at large.
- ii. **Researchers and Students:** From the findings of this research, researchers will benefit immensely as it will provide them with the needed data to deal with the issues of ecological hazards and its consequences on biodiversity conservation especially in ONELGA. It will also provide the students and researchers with materials for further research on biodiversity conservation and ecological hazards in ONELGA.
- iii. **Government and Non-Governmental Organizations:** This research will be of great benefits to the government and non-governmental organizations. It will be useful in designing of programmes that are capable of addressing ecological hazards and its impacts on different biological species. It will also be beneficial to them in evidence-based policy, advocacy and public awareness creation on biodiversity and ecological hazards, and how to prevent the adverse effects of ecological hazards on biodiversity. Therefore, this research hopes to equip the government and non-governmental organizations with the needed information for public policy making, appropriate legislation and mitigation strategies on the impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation in ONELGA, Rivers State, Nigeria.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this study captured the relationship between the independent variable (ecological hazards which includes its nature, causes, impacts and solutions), and the dependent variable (biodiversity conservation which includes reduction in bushing burning, introduction of extinct species, increasing communication, education and public awareness programmes). It also shows the intervening variables which is as a result of the independent variable such as education, mitigation, adaptation etc.

2.1.1 Concept of Ecosystem

The word 'ecosystem' was coined in 1930 by Roy Dapham to show the physical and biological components of an environment and their relationship with each other as a unit. Ecosystem refers to an area or geographical location that includes the biotic factors (living organisms), and the abiotic factors (which is the physical environment). The two factors function together. One can't do without the other; they complement each other. An ecosystem consists of plants, animals, microbes, soil rocks, minerals, water sources, the local atmosphere and most importantly humans, in an interactive relationship. The abiotic factors and the biotic factors interact as one and are linked together through the processes of nutrient cycling in nature and energy flows. For instance, the energy from sun is trapped by plants and used during the process of photosynthesis.

Photosynthesis is a biological process through which plants make or produce their own food through the help of sunlight, carbon dioxide and water (inorganic sources). Plants in turn, serve as food for animals and humans (organisms) that are not capable of manufacturing their own food. When these organisms feed on the plants, energy and nutrients are transferred to them, and then flows to the next consumer. Dead organic matter is then broken down by decomposers such as fungi and bacteria, thereby recycling and releasing nutrients in a soluble form. This forms part of the materials for nutrient cycling or for the use of other organisms. (Biology Dictionary: <https://www.biologydictionary-ecosystem/>) The ecosystem is of two types; the terrestrial and the aquatic ecosystems.

2.1.2. Concept of Biodiversity

The word 'biodiversity' is relatively new which was coined as a combination of two terms 'biological' and 'diversity' by Laura Tanglely in 1985. In contemporary times, biodiversity as a concept has achieved general acceptability and usage by different authors in the field of biological sciences and other related fields in the natural and environmental sciences.

Biodiversity refers to the variety of life on earth. This consists of all organisms, species, and the human population. It also refers to the genetic variations among these organisms and their complex assemblage of communities and the ecosystem. Biological diversity is found in the biosphere. This is the part of the atmosphere where life is found. Biological species found on earth today includes many millions of different (biological) species' interactions of approximately four billion years of evolution (UNEP, 2010)

Oribhabor (2016) defined biodiversity as a term used to refer to the total number of different living organisms which consists of plants, animals, fungi and microbes that are found on planet earth. It is the equality of genes, species and ecosystems in a region. He furthermore stated that "it is a term used to describe the number, variety and variability of living organisms." Previously, the human species were treated separately from the rest of nature, but massive review of our current knowledge on the elaborate field of biological diversity conducted by UNEP considers humans as an important part, as well as a critical part of the earth's biodiversity.

Biodiversity is also seen as the variety and variability of life on earth. It is typically a measure of variation of organisms at the genetic, species and ecosystem levels. The terrestrial biodiversity is usually greater near the equator as a result of warm climate and high primary productivity. Along the coast, marine biodiversity is usually the highest.

According to the Fifth National Biodiversity Report (FNBR, 2015), Nigerians biodiversity constitutes the sources of food, raw materials, wide range of goods and services and genetic materials for agriculture, medicines and health-care support; domestic and commercial products, aesthetics and cultural values among others.

The United Nations Earth Summit (UNES, 1992) defined biological diversity as the variability among living organisms, from all sources including inter-alia; terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complex of which they are part. This includes diversity with species, between species and of ecosystems.

2.1.3. Types of Biodiversity

According to UNEP (2010), biodiversity is of three levels or types. They include the genetic diversity, species diversity and the ecosystem diversity.

Genetic Diversity

According to Sohler (2019), the genetic diversity refers to all the various genes. This is the basic unit of hereditary and variation that is found in a locus on a chromosome and is also found in all living species including individual plants, animals, fungi, microbes as well as the human species. It is the totality of the genetic features in the genetic makeup of species. This is a

reflection of the similarities and the differences in the genes. This covers distinct population of a single species such as thousands of breeds of different organism.

Genetic diversity contributes to the ability of species to respond to environmental change. For instance, where some individuals have the capacity to endure and survive a particular unfavourable change in the environment, such as increasing pollution in the environment, some do not have it such surviving ability. This may result in large damage or proper functioning of the internal organs or may lead to death from such condition. This shows that the ones that can adapt to such environment are much better than those that couldn't. Those that do not have the capacity to survive may suffered damage or die. This process is called natural selecting. Therefore, genetic diversity can in a way tackle natural selection for a better environment and conservation.

Species Diversity

This is a type of biological diversity of different species as well as the variation within and between different species (UNES, 2019). It is the totality of different species that are represented in a given community. According to the Encyclopedia of Earth (2019), species diversity is a measurement of the total number of species found in a particular habitat or community at large. It also refers to the specie richness and how evenly species' abundance is distributed in an ecosystem. Species diversity is very significant in an ecosystem as it assures its longevity. When a specie is lost, it affects many other species thereby causing imbalance in the ecosystem. Species interact with the environment and therefore performs certain functions. One could be increasing the availability of light for plant growth and preventing sediment erosion. The death or loss of a specie in an ecosystem is in the biosphere, and is accompanied by a loss of functionality which directly affects human life in a severe way. Reduction of commercially used fish stocks, soil erosion and sediment are two examples. This is why Sohler (2009) insisted on the necessity to conserve the species diversity.

Ecosystem Diversity

Ecosystem diversity consist of all the various habitat, biological entities, niches, communities and their interactions, as well as the differences with the individual resulting in the ecological process found in the biosphere. This includes both the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystem. It is a habitat that incorporates both habitat and community diversity. A habitat is where an organism lives or where it can be found. A community comprises of plants, animals, other microorganisms as well as humans and the environment interacting with each one another. Inherent in ecosystem diversity is the biotic (living organisms) and the abiotic (non-living components) which makes it different from the genetic and species diversity. Ecosystem diversity shows the relationship between the biotic and abiotic components of the environment.

While the genetic and species diversity portrays only the biotic component, their functionality and adaptation among others.

2.1.4. Concept of Ecological Hazards

Ecological hazard of different sort is seen as a number one threat and outstanding challenge facing the global community and as such, it has been given different definitions by different authors according to their perceptions and the way it affects them.

Hazards are anything that could cause potential harm or danger to persons or personal property. It is anything, substance or event that could cause harm to the things around. Ecological hazards are subsequently interchanged with environmental challenges, problems, hazards, disasters and/or calamities in environmental literatures. Environmental hazard is anything from the interactive relationship between the biotic components of the ecosystem, the abiotic component and the immediate environment that poses danger or harm. Environmental challenge is any form of harm, danger, peril, predicament or any risk of loss in the immediate environment. (Petters,1995). Human kind are presently facing problems, some of which are climate change, shortage in clean and accessible fresh water, ecosystem degradation, soil erosion and mostly biodiversity loss. (Chen, 2005).

Most scholars in the field of biological sciences defined ecological challenges or hazards as occurrences that are harmful or potentially dangerous to man and his immediate environment (Jay and Scott, 2011; Wright and Boorse, 2011; Mahatma, 2009; Enger and Smith, 2010). Environmental degradation and deterioration have been taking place for thousands of years as biological species began to find ways of living and surviving on earth (Kwame, 2008). An environmental challenge can be said to be an unexpected accident resulting from natural or man-made factors (or a combination of both factors) that has an adverse or negative impact on the daily lives and living condition of living organisms i.e. humans, flora, fauna and microorganism (Mary, 1995). Ecological hazard or challenge refers to the activities of nature and human or a collaboration of both that makes the immediate environment of biological species unfriendly and unfavourable (Hyde and Reeve, 2011). It is a change in the natural ecosystem usually from good to bad. These changes are negative as it does not favour the living organisms in that environment.

2.1.5 Classification of Environmental Challenges

Environmental challenges may be broadly grouped into major and minor depending on their ability to cause little or adverse damage to biological species, property and the environment (Joseph, 2009). Furthermore, environmental challenges are classified under the broad title of natural and artificial, based solely on their mode of occurrence. Natural events usually occur

suddenly and swiftly, also cause severe damage to living organisms and the environment at large (Santra, 2011). Artificial events on the other hand are influenced or produced by humans. They contain some human induced factors human errors, ignorance, negligence, intents etc. Uche (1995) noted that the earth as an ecosystem has a small or terminal broad line within which it can effectively absorb or withstand the impacts or effects resulting from within or without it, to avoid dangerous deterioration and overstrain.

2.1.6. Causes of Biodiversity Loss in Onelga

Environmental and ecological hazards are the major causes of biodiversity losses in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area. These are threats to biological species. Ecological hazards are caused by natural forces (astronomical), and human influences or interferences (anthropogenic) or a combination of both forces. The natural causes of ecological hazards resulting in biodiversity losses include climatic, geological, atmospheric, disease and biological factors. Natural ecological hazards can also come from geological, meteorological and biological events or incidents (Coenrads, 2009). Coenrads (2009) also noted that geological events erupt as a result of the inherent functioning and movement of the planet; while meteorological events occur as a result of the differences in the global weather patterns. On the other hand, biological events are caused by the actions of living organisms or agents. Similarly, Petters (1995) submitted that while some natural disasters arise from the instability inherent in the working of the planets; others are as a result of the mass loss of earth's materials. Wright and Boorse (2011) identified the causes of natural hazards to include hydrological, meteorological and geological forces.

Biodiversity loss can also be caused by anthropogenic forces. These are human activities or interferences. According to UNEP (2010), the main causes of biodiversity loss include the following:

1. **Habitat Loss and Destruction:** This is one of the greatest threats to biodiversity. Habitat loss is directly linked to human induced pressure on land by their daily activities such as agriculture, fishing, livestock rearing and hunting.
2. **Invasive Alien Species:** The introduction of exotic species that replaced local and native species is cited as the second largest cause of biodiversity loss. Alien invasive species replace, and often result in the extinction of native species. These invasive species also inhibit ecological processes and reduces the value of the environment. This limits the livelihood options available to human beings living and depending on such ecosystem (NFNBR, 2015).

3. **Pollution and Contamination:** Biological systems respond slowly to changes in their environment. Pollution and contamination result in irreversible damage to species. Human's activities and interferences with the natural ecosystem are solely responsible for the pollution and contamination of the environment. The pollution and contamination of the coastal and marine ecosystem with the use of oil, chemicals, wastes from industries, pesticides, herbicides and fertilizers washed down by running water into the large bodies of water habiting biological species of different sorts. Species are lost in these processes. According to Anon (1984), Nigeria needs 1.6 million tons of fish protein annually. Unfortunately, her national fish output is only 400,000 tons annually. This is due to unsustainable harvesting, contamination and incidences of pollution of its sources especially the marine habitat.

The pollution of the atmosphere has become uncondusive to biological species whose habitat is the aerial ecosystem. This is also applicable to other biological species like humans and animals. Challenges of gas flaring, bush burning, burning of fossil fuels like crude oil, coal and natural gas which supply most energy needed to run vehicles, generate electricity for industries (industrialization and urbanization) as well as household etc. have contributed to the rise in Green House Gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere. Green House Gases (GHGs) is triggered by the high level of carbon dioxide and the low level of oxygen in the atmosphere (Charles, 2010). Mining and exploration for petroleum products, land reclamation, deforestation (timber harvesting), over-grazing, erosion, road construction, ranching, uncontrolled poaching and other human activities have also escalated pollution and soil contamination. These pollution, contamination and other related activities have led to the fragmentation of habitats, and the subsequent disappearances and losses of many species of flora and fauna. (Madu 2007; Asthana and Asthana, 2013; Oribhabor, 2016).

4. **Alternations in Ecosystem Composition:** Assemblage of species and their interactions within their ecosystem is critical for not only saving the species, but also for their successful future evolution. In the event of alternation, either within species groups or within the environment, the entire ecosystem can begin to change. Alternations to ecosystem are critical factors contributing to species and habitat losses.
5. **Over-Exploitation:** Over-hunting, over fishing or over-collecting of species can quickly lead to their decline. Humans are solely responsible for these. Negative changes in the consumption pattern of humans have been cited as the key reason for this unsustainable exploitation of natural resources.

6. **Global Climate Change:** One of the major ecological hazards threatening biodiversity is the issue of climate change. Both climate variability and climate change cause biodiversity loss. Species and populations may be lost permanently if they are not provided with enough time to adapt to changing climatic conditions. According to De Chavez and Tauli-Corpus (2008), global warming is what actually induces the change in climate. Scientists have noted that the average temperature of the earth has increased by 0.74 degrees Celsius over the past 100 years. In the absence of no action to control this, there will be more rise in the earth's temperature to the extent that it will be difficult to cope with it. This shows the seriousness of the threat posed by climate change to countries that depend mostly on climate sensitive resources for sustenance of livelihood and overall development. Temperature is a major part of ecological hazards ravaging the globe. However, the seriousness and gravity of other hazards cannot be overemphasized. Temperature rise is very visible in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area due to gas flaring and other mechanical and industrial activities.

The rapid growth in the world population is a major cause of many environmental problems and challenges (Madu, 2009). Population growth is also a threat to biodiversity loss. Population size and rate of growth have led to the increase in the demand for food, clean water and energy increase. Moreover, poor people's reliance on natural resources and the lack of alternatives to which to turn to in times of stress have led to high level of use which degrades the very asset on which their survival depends on.

The Nigerian Fifth National Biodiversity Reports (NFNBR, 2015) stated that threats to biodiversity which in turn leads to its loss includes habitat depredation, unsustainable agricultural practices, unsustainable harvesting and their activities, poaching, fuel wood consumption, illegal logging. Other causes of biodiversity losses include: uncontrolled, illegal and bad mining practices, unsustainable harvesting of non-timber forest products, pollution, gas flaring, invasive species, over-grazing and bush fires. The USAID (Report, 2008) also indicated that degradation of habitats and loss of species are not always as visible as its conversion. However, biodiversity loss usually occurs in other more insidious ways with equally damaging results.

Orihabor (2016) emphasized mainly on the aquatic ecosystem. According to him, the biodiversity of the Nigerian aquatic ecosystem is increasingly being destroyed or depleted by persistent threat of aquatic pollution. The depletion is mainly caused by intense human activities such as indiscriminate use of fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides in agriculture and industrialization. Pressure due to rapid population growth also lead to the destruction of biodiversity. Land reclamation which depletes hitherto large water bodies also caused

the destruction the ecosystem of biological species. Anthropogenic causes of biodiversity loss such as over-exploitation, pollution and contaminations are visible in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers state. Also, The UNEP (2011) affirmed that pollution has become one of the most serious problems of our time. Specifically, water pollution is one of the prime reasons for the loss of aquatic genetic diversity. It was also reported that the pollution of soil by petroleum hydrocarbons in Ogoni-land, Rivers State is extensive in land areas, sediments and swamp pond. This is also applicable in ONELGA.

2.1.7 Impact/Consequences of Ecological Hazards on Biodiversity

Biodiversity are found in the environment and play important roles in the environment and also in the existence of biological species found in it. Ecological hazards pose unprecedented challenges on biodiversity because of the natural functioning of the earth and the interference of humans on the ecosystem. The effects of ecological hazards on biodiversity are complex and multi-dimensional. They vary from place to place and from time to time. According to Cunningham and Cunningham (2006), ecological hazards have widespread impacts in world and on other organisms within it. They affect all biological species and biotic components of the environment such as humans, flora, fauna. They also affect the abiotic components especially the immediate environment.

The emergence of human beings on earth has displayed an ongoing biodiversity reduction. This is accompanied with the loss of genetic diversity named the 'Holocene Extinction'. The reduction is caused primarily by human impacts; particularly habitat destruction. Conversely, biodiversity positively impacts the health of human being in a number of ways, although a few negative effects are studied. On the negative side, ecological hazards make existence unconducive and unbearable for biological species. When the tolerance range of these biological species have reached its maximum level, they leave that environment for a favourable environment for survival. This migration oftentimes results in extinction. Presently, just about 1% of different species of flora and fauna exist because of extinction. Therefore, biodiversity losses are mostly caused by both astronomical and anthropogenic forces.

The major consequence of ecological hazard is biodiversity loss. Others include fresh water degradation, climate change, stratospheric ozone depletion, land degradation, deforestation and coastal degradation. Other aftermaths are climate change, hydrological upset, disease outbreaks and stratospheric ozone depletion. Environmental hazards are of major concern to individuals, governments and non-governmental organizations at local and international levels. Desertification for example, is responsible for the attendant depletion of resources

based in the affected places. It brings about decline in soil fertility and cause population displacement of biological species. Flooding causes aesthetic deformation, environmental pollution and destruction of farm lands. Similarly, pollution degrades the quality of the environment and soil erosion leads to reduction in farm productivity. Erosion also leads to formation of bad land gullies in mining and dereliction cases. The consequence of desert encroachment includes climate change, loss of vegetal cover, soil depletion, crop failure and displacement of biological species' population. Similarly, ozone layer depletion and global warming are the outcome of arson, burning of waste, bushing burning and associated environmental crimes.

The issues of biodiversity loss are closely linked to issue of climate change. The impact of climate induced biodiversity change on humans, animals and plants' health are of major concerns to biological experts. This is because of the potentially height cost associated with both emerging zoonotic diseases and changes in the distribution of disease vectors. Changes in agricultural practices have been strongly linked to the emergence of a number of zoonotic diseases (Charles, 2006). Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area is also impacted in these ways.

Orihabor and Ogbulebu (2016) observed that ecological hazards impact negatively on the aquatic ecosystem resulting in the changes in water quality, longitudinal distribution of species and reduction in the abundance and diversity of macro-benthic invertebrates. Mustapha (2006) reported that the effect of human activities on biodiversity of a tropical man-made lake results in the high level of depletion. The rapid increase in the concentration of nitrate in the lake, low species of plankton and fish deaths probably occurring from obnoxious fishing practices, and poor water quality are human activities on biodiversity. Ecological impacts triggered anthropogenic activities on predation and fish assemblages of the tidal creek in the Niger Delta. This leads to the depletion of the ecological habitat and drastic reduction in tax and abundance of species in the region and particularly in Ogba/Ndoni/Egbema Local Government Area. Bernard and Munam (2013) observed that there is a high level of magnesium, iron, lead, calcium and nickel than lotto and son beyond permitted maximum levels for dining water.

Due to ecological hazards, cases of mass extinction have been recorded as the environment changes and unfavourable environments. More than 99.9percent of all species that ever lived on earth amounting to over five billion species, are estimated to be extinct. The 2019 Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services by (IPBES, 2019) noted that 25% of plants and animals' species are threatened with extinction as a result of human activities and interferences with the natural environment. The inherent working of

the planet, combined with the activities of human beings have led to the deterioration of nature at an unprecedented and accelerating rate. This has also led to biodiversity loss. The main drivers of this deterioration have been changes in land and sea use, exploitation of living beings, climate change, pollution, and invasive species. These five drivers are also caused by societal behaviours, especially consumption and governance.

Conclusively, the severity of ecological hazards in Nigeria and its impacts on biodiversity have been documented by scholars like Petters (1995); Franca (2002); and Tyokumbur (2010). They reported that the consequences of ecological hazard in Nigeria include damages in infrastructure, loss of life, injury, loss of housing, loss of crops, breakdown of social order, disruption of communication as well as epidemiological threats. These impacts are also prevalent Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State.

2.1.8 Conservation of Biodiversity

In recent times, biodiversity in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of River State is facing threats as a result of careless and ignorant activities by human beings, as well as natural occurring events in the environment. Generally, biodiversity can be conserved if ecological hazard is being controlled and mitigated. The adaptation and mitigation of ecological hazards in the environment is very paramount in the conservation of biodiversity caused by anthropogenic forces. The conservation of biodiversity matters a lot as it provides substantial benefits to meeting immediate human needs. Human needs such as clean water, consistent water flows, protection from floods, storms and stable climate etc. are achieved through biodiversity conservation. Biodiversity loss is dangerous and its consequences are immediate. Loss of biodiversity creates fewer opportunities for livelihoods, better health, education and better living conditions. It also results in fewer fishes in the sea. This means less food for human survival. There will also be lack of clean water, forest resources such as foods and decreased plants for medicine. In the long term, it also means less income for poor communities (UNEP, 2010). Therefore, the conservation and protection of biodiversity in ONELGA is of paramount importance to the sustainable livelihood of the people of the council.

Biodiversity, ecosystem services and human wellbeing are highly related to conservation. Conservation of biodiversity is the centred around strategic plans to protect the organisms in the ecosystem and the general preservation of the entire global ecological network. A strategic conservation plan that are designed to engage public policy experts, biologists and community leaders will be helpful in preservation of the entire ecosystems, cultures and all biological species. Cultural and biological diversity are intimately related to each other. If

we lose one, we risk losing the other. The diversity of societies, cultures and languages that have developed throughout human history is intimately related to biological diversity and its use.

Biodiversity plays vital role in societal support system. It provides the basic resources for socio-economic activities in the country (Nwachukwu, 2002). However, societal support system in ONELGA have had series of devastations as a result of natural catastrophes and human activities. To save the environment from further degradation of rich and exhaustive resources, and biodiversity loss; challenges posed by biodiversity loss should be addressed. This will enable the society to achieve environmental sustainability and reduced occurrences of biodiversity loss and extinction.

Raven, Berg and Hassenshall (2010), the elements that contribute to addressing environmental problem and prevent biodiversity losses to include scientific assessment, risk analysis, political action, long-term evaluation and public education and involvement. However, they opined that solving these problems hardly considered these mechanisms. From the reviews of various experts' opinions and suggestions; astronomical and anthropogenic causes of biodiversity losses be addressed through conservation and mitigations processes in the following ways:

1. **The Green Economy Initiative:** The Green Economy Initiative has been defined as one which will accelerate the transition to a low-carbon, resource-efficient economy able to meet multiple challenges and deliver multiple opportunities in the 21th century. Scholars believe that this can help to solve the problems of pollution and environmental degradation thereby ensuring the conservation of biodiversity in the society.
2. **Conservation of Natural Resources:** Conservation of natural resources on its own is a way of conserving biodiversity. The proper use of resources and low reliance on natural resources in the environment, and other options as alternatives to which humans to turn in time of stress could help reduce the degradation of the very asset on which the survival of biological species depends on. This helps to reduce the event of biodiversity extinction and loss. The natural resources include land, water, minerals, energy, forest wealth, wildlife, population resources and biodiversity. Environmental experts believe that proper management and conservation of these natural resources protect biodiversity and lower the occurrences of its loss.
3. **Proper Agricultural Practices:** Overcoming environmental challenges and ensuring conservation practices demands the enhancement of agricultural production without compromising the natural ecosystem of biological species. Improper agricultural practices such as over-cropping, over-grazing, over-hunting, too much application of

pesticides, herbicides and fertilizers by human degrades the environment thereby affecting biodiversity in the environment. If farmers in ONELGA in Rivers State involve themselves in proper agricultural practices, there will be no occurrence of degradation and deterioration of the natural ecosystem. Also, biodiversity loss will not be experienced. Similarly, cases of crop failures or low yields arising from climate variability occasioned by the delay in the onset of rain and the increasing length, and frequency of dry spells during the growing seasons will not be heard.

4. **Implementation on Policy/Agreements:** There should also be an increased focus on the implementation of multilateral environment agreements related to biodiversity conservation such as the Convention on Biological Species (CBD). The convention informally known as the Biodiversity Convention, opened for signature at the Earth's Summit in Rio de Janeiro in Brazil, on June 5, 1992; entered into force on December 29, 1993. The summit produced a multilateral treaty which has three main goals of conservation of biological diversity; the sustainable use of its components; and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from genetic resources. The main objective was to develop national strategies for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity. Others summits for biodiversity conservation were the Convention on International Trade on Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (ITES); The Convention on Migratory Species (CMS) and the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, and the World Heritage Convention. Strict observation and implementation of these agreements made by these multilateral conventions at national, state and local levels of government, non-governmental organizations, community-based organizations as well as individuals, would reduce the risk of biodiversity loss and environmental degradation.
5. **Communication, Education and Public Awareness (CEPA):** Increased communication, education and public awareness, proper and sound environmental education programmes, workshop, seminars etc. would help to create the needed awareness for biodiversity conservation. This will help to connect the people with the environment through biodiversity conservation. This process will also help to educate and inform the people on the need to take care of the environment in order to safeguard their livelihoods. The significance of this lies in the protection of these natural resources, living organisms and the benefits thereof for societal sustainability development.
6. **Mitigation of Anthropogenic Challenges:** The mitigation of anthropogenic challenges is dependent on its types, causes and consequences. For instance, curtailing man-induced desertification requires measures like irrigation farming, agro-forestry,

rotational grazing, prevention of illegal falling of trees, controlled use of wood as source of fuel and energy, afforestation and re-afforestation programmes. Also, man-influenced flood can be controlled through channelization and regular clearance of drainage channels, urban planning, sustainable waste management, as well as environmental sanitation. In the same vein, the control of soil erosion takes the form of cover cropping, contour ploughing, controlled grazing, terracing, and creation of shelter belts. This shows that disaster management is all encompassing for biodiversity conservation. It entails respect and care for the environment as well as periodic Environmental Impact Assessment (Ibimilua and Ibimilua, 2014)

7. **Removal of Exotic Invasive Species (Protection and Restoration Techniques):** The removal of exotic species will allow for the species that they have been negatively impacted to recover their ecological niches. Exotic species that have become pests can be identified taxonomically using the barcode of life. This can be done using the Digital Automation Identification System (DAISY). Removal of exotic invasive species is done only in a large group of individuals due to the economic cost. As sustainable population of the remaining native species in an area become assured. Missing species that are candidates for re-introduction can be identified using databases such as the ‘Encyclopedia of Life’ and the ‘Global Biodiversity Information Facility’. Reintroduction is done by:

- i. Gene banks are collections of specimens and genetic materials. Some banks intend to reintroduce banked species to the ecosystem.
- ii. Reduction and better targeting of pesticides that allow more species to survive in agricultural and urbanized areas.
- iii. Location specific approaches may be less useful for protection of migratory species. One approach is to create wildlife corridors that correspond to the animals’ movement. National and other boundaries can complicate corridor creation.

Other ways include:

1. Identifying and creating opportunities for rural enterprises based on biodiversity such as eco-tourism, bio-prospecting to benefit local communities, the environment, species and their habitat.
2. Encouraging development that is sustainable and based on biodiversity by drawing attention to regions that might otherwise be developed in an unsustainable way.
3. Providing important economic and social benefits that provide local communities and incentives for habitat protection.

4. Identification of options for sharing the benefits of conservation and sustainable use with local communities and stakeholders. (UNEP, 2010).
5. Environmental monitoring with the use of satellites, geographical legislations, disaster forecasting and mitigation as well as environmental risk assessment and mapping. On the other hand, the management of man-induced challenges requires poverty alleviation, control of population growth, recycling of materials and resources, reduction of arms race as well as woman empowerment. These are some of the scholarly contributions to biodiversity conservations.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

This research is anchored on the ‘Anthropogenic Global Warming’ (AGW) theory. The Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory is used to connect the challenges and issues surrounding the environment including the ecosystems, atmosphere and especially biological diversity. The Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory was proposed by Joseph Fourier in 1824. It was discovered in 1860 by John Tyndall. It was further investigated and expanded to the generally and universally known and acceptable standard in this present time by Svante August in 1896, who was a Swedish Scientist. The Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory explained how human related activities cause damage to the environment/ecosystem thereby affecting the existence of biodiversity through the activities of burning of bushes, fossil fuels, pollution and contamination, deforestation, transportation, industrialization, etc.

Anthropogenic Global Warming theory explains that human’s daily activities result in the daily release or emission of Green House Gases (GHGs). These Green House Gases include Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), Nitrous oxide (NO₂), Ozone (O₃), Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and Water Vapour (H₂O). These gases are emitted into the environment, particularly the atmosphere in large quantities. While in the atmosphere, they alter the natural buildup of the environment as well as the natural climatic order (Blast, 2010; Ada-Wilson, 2017). These alternations affect or have negative impacts on biodiversity in the environment.

The sun’s energy travels through space and reaches the earth’s atmosphere that is transparent to the incoming sunlight thereby allowing it to penetrate the surface to the planet. The sunlight allowed to penetrate the planets’ surface is absorbed and reflected back as heat into the atmosphere. When this happens, certain gases trapped into the atmosphere called the Green House Gases (GHGs) absorbs the outgoing reflected and internal thermal radiation, resulting in earth’s atmospheric temperature becoming warmer than expected.

Blast (2016) called this the mechanism of enhanced Green House Gas effect. Most cases of biodiversity loss and events of extinction are within the context of Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory directly or indirectly.

Also, it is argued that the activities of human beings which have an influence on the environment is not only on its Green House Gas emission along. This also includes the transformation and changing of the earth's surface (environment and ecosystem). There are also other forces besides Green House Gases. Pielke (2008) outline these forces to include urban heat islands, aerosols, ozone, deforestation, coastal development, jet contrails. Blast (2010) holds that these forces have greater impacts on climate change which alters the natural buildup of the environment thereby affecting biological diversity in the environment than the Green House Gases (GHGs). The alternation and deterioration of the environment and the earth's cities cause damage to the environment and biological species found in it.

While the Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory concentrated mainly on human's activities and interferences with the natural environment that has adverse impact on biodiversity, there are also natural causes of ecological hazards and biodiversity loss. These are natural occurring activities of the planet which cause variation and changes in the environment. These are also important. Nevertheless, these human influences are much more significant and outstanding and involves diverse ranges of first order of ecological hazards in an ecosystem.

The relevance of Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory to this research is its relationship to the causes of ecological hazards and biodiversity loss. It has been state that ecological hazards and biodiversity loss are mainly caused by both astronomical and anthropogenic forces. However, human activities, influences and interferences with the natural environment are more pervasive and prevalent. This makes the environment unfavourable for biological species to leave in.

Another theory that backs this research up is the Theory of Human Forcing's besides Green House Gases. The second theory of ecological hazards and its impacts on biological diversity contends that mankind's greatest influence on climate is not its Green House Gases emission, but its transformation of earth's surface by clearing forest, irrigating deserts, and building cities. Although the natural causes of ecological hazards and biodiversity loss are undoubtedly important, the human influence are significant and involves a diverse range of first-order environment destroyers, but not limited to, the human input of carbon dioxide (Roger PielkeSr, 2008) the following are some of these human

forcing other than Green House Gases, they are; Urban heat islands, Aerosols and ozone, deforestation, Coastal development, jet contrails (Pielke, 2008, Blast 2010).

In ONELGA, humans also engage in some unfriendly activities such as bush burning, transportation, deforestation, burning of fossil fuels, gas flaring, industrialization etc. which results in the emission of Green House Gases in the atmosphere. These Green House Gases' emission causes changes in the environment such as change in pattern of temperature, high and low rainfall intensity etc. These changes have a negative impact on the environment and also affects biodiversity. Also, human activities such as over-exploitation, pollution and contamination, gas flaring as well as natural occurrences have an adverse impact on the ecosystem, specifically on biodiversity. It is therefore, pertinent for governments (at local, state and national levels), non-governmental organizations, community based organizations and individuals to inform, educate and create awareness among the people in understanding the consequences of their activities, the effect of Green House Gas emission on the environment and biodiversity. They should also be educated on the importance of conserving, protecting and sustaining biodiversity and the natural resources. Necessary measures to help mitigate ecological hazards and reduce the rate of biodiversity loss and extinction in the ONELGA, and the capacity to adapt to already made changes should be made available to citizens by governments and concerned stakeholders. The use of the Anthropogenic Global Warming (AGW) theory in this research is therefore significant in the quest to provide a template for biodiversity conservation in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State.

2.3. Related Empirical Studies

Recent researches have studied the impact of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation. Unfortunately, none of them addressed the peculiar challenges of biodiversity conservation in ONELGA. The United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2010) used a descriptive analysis to explain the nature of biodiversity and the effects of ecological hazards biodiversity extinction. The study describes and relates biodiversity to the variety of life on earth. It includes all organisms, species and population, genetic variation among them, and their complex assemblages of communities and ecosystem. The study further submitted that many millions of distinct biological species are the product of four billion years of evolution. Majority of these species have gone into extinction due to unfriendly changes in the natural environment. The work further identified habitat and destruction, alternation in ecosystem composition, invasive alien species, over-exploitation, pollution and contamination, and global climate change as major causes of biodiversity losses.

Ibimilua and Ibimilua (2014) used a descriptive analysis to demonstrate the process that leads to changes in the natural environment. The work helps in a better understanding of the challenges of biodiversity loss. The study defined environmental hazard or challenge as any form of danger, predicament, harm or risk of loss in the environment. It further noted that natural forces and the anthropogenic or the uncontrolled interaction between humans and the natural world caused biodiversity loss. Specific problems like oil spillage coastal erosion, flooding and pollution are rampant consequences of these hazards. The study advocated for the collaborative efforts of international organizations, governments, non-government organizations, environmental managers, future leaders, planners, technologists and other decision makers in halting the frequency, magnitude and consequences of the environmental challenges.

Madu (2007) identified rapid overgrowing world population as a major reason for the loss of biodiversity as well as a constituent of ecological hazard in our environment. High population size, and growth rate lead to an increase in the demand of food, clean water and source of livelihood. In the bid to meet these needs, there is over-reliance on natural resources in the environment as alternatives. This helps in the degradation and threat on organisms in the environment and the natural ecosystem at large. Also, some of man's care-free activities and attitudes pose danger to the environment which could lead to the extinction of biological species.

Oribhabor (2016) work was mainly centred on aquatic biodiversity. He submitted that the decline in biodiversity of aquatic ecosystem is largely caused by human activities that poses serious threat to the environment. He further said that the human race has 850 million members when it entered the industrial age, sharing earth with life forms nearly as diverse as the plant has ever possessed. Unfortunately, biological resources have drastically reduced in the 21st century. Biodiversity is the term used to describe the total variety of living organisms (plants, animals, fungi and microbes) that exist on this planet. The biodiversity of Nigeria's aquatic ecosystem is increasingly being destroyed or depleted by persistent threat of growth; sediment pollution, organic pollution, eutrophication, acidification, heavy metals and organochlorines, thermal pollution, nuclear pollution, human introductions (voluntary or accidental) and oil pollution. This is the aftermath of intense human activities such as indiscriminate use fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture, industrialization, urbanization, pressure due to rapid population growth; misutilization and mismanagement of natural aquatic resource; dam, roads and bridges construction; irrigation; draining and filling of wetlands; petroleum exploration, exploitation and refining as well as transportation, storage, marketing and use of petroleum products. The rapid decline in biodiversity of aquatic ecosystems in Nigeria could be reversed by protecting

the existing resources based on the carrying capacity of the ecosystem. The work recommended engineering solutions based on sound scientific evaluation and ecological awareness.

Nigeria Fifth National Biodiversity Report (NFNBR, 2015) reported the status of biodiversity and its contributions to various sectors of Nigerian economy including tourism, agriculture, water resources, health, commerce and industrial development. The report identified sources of food, raw materials for agriculture, medicine and health, care support, domestic and commercial products, aesthetics and cultural heritages as basic values of biodiversity to Nigeria's socio-economic development. Biodiversity provides ecosystem services that improve the value and knowledge about life. The value of biodiversity is closely linked to the wide range of the various ecosystems found. The study outlined biodiversity species' statistics in Nigeria as mammals 274; birds 941; amphibians 109; reptiles 135; inland fishes 338; (314 species for Niger Delta alone); orchids 145; flowering plants 5209; as well as biodiversity sites. The work outlined the threats to biodiversity as habitat degradation, unsustainable agricultural practices, unsustainable harvesting of bio resources, extractive industries and their activities, unsustainable natural resource harvesting, poaching, firewood consumption, illegal logging, uncontrolled illegal and bad mining practices, unsustainable harvesting of non-timber product, gas flaring, pollution, overgrazing, bush fire etc. These works helped to give this research a direction and focus in its quest to contribute to the body of literature in this area of study.

2.8. Summary of Related Literature

Studies have shown that the conservation of biodiversity as well as the level of awareness on issues of ecological hazard and biodiversity loss is still at a very low pace in Rivers State. The awareness level of biodiversity conservation in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area have been very insignificant. The need to create massive awareness on the impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation in ONELGA propelled this research endeavour. With respect to ONELGA, the nature, causes and consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity have not been addressed. This research intends to fill this gap in literature and provide an ample knowledge on how citizens in the local government can protect and conserve biodiversity and the entire ecosystem for their benefits and sustainable development. Such knowledge through awareness creation will help to reduce the risk of biodiversity loss or extinction. The review of related empirical literature helped in identifying the gap in literature and objectively project the work to fill the identified gap in knowledge.

Furthermore, in addition to scholarly contributions to this field of study; an in-depth knowledge of ecological hazards and its effect on biodiversity will help the local people to be well

informed on ways of biodiversity conservation. Also, available technologies that will help in mitigating ecological hazard should be brought to the knowledge of the people. Cases of over-population should be thoroughly looked into, and ways to tackle and reduce the ever-growing population of the world should be activated. These are areas this work will help in filling the gap in literature.

The importance and relevance of biodiversity cannot be overemphasized. It is therefore, important to conserve and protect biodiversity of different habitats and ecosystems by stopping and preventing some activities. This is because the anthropogenic factors have been seen as major causes of ecological hazard resulting in biodiversity loss. Notwithstanding, the astronomical factor have been very active and potent too. Controlling and managing these factors that affect the environment is very important in order for the people to enjoy the benefits of biodiversity and its conservation. This, in no doubt will benefit all and bring back the environment to its formal natural state.

Presently, there is no available literature on biodiversity conservation in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Also, the causes and impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation have not been documented in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area by researchers in the fields of biological and environmental sciences. Therefore, there is a gap in literature that needs to be filled in this regard. The research intends finding out the different biological species, types of ecological hazards most prevalent in ONELGA, the causes and consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation in the local government in order to fill the identified gap in literature and contribute to knowledge in this area of study. At the end of the study, strategies for mitigation and adaptation in the conservation of biodiversity against ecological hazards will be recommended.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the step-by-step procedures employed in carrying out the study of Ecological Hazards and Biodiversity in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The research methodology will be presented under the following sub-headings: design of the study; area of the study; population of the study; sample and sampling techniques; instrument for data collection; validation of the instrument; reliability of the instrument; administration and collection of the instrument; and method of data analysis.

3.1. Design of the Study

This research adopts a descriptive design and survey method. The utilization of both the descriptive design and survey method in a researched endeavour is called “descriptive survey design”. According to Nwahunanya (2009) a descriptive survey design is aimed at describing, explaining and detailing the current state of affairs as they exist at the time of the study. It is also a process of gathering data in order to answer questions concerning the current state of the researched problem. In descriptive survey, proper evaluation of data obtained from the field survey rests on proper evaluation of empirical data. The findings of the study are usually presented descriptively and logically. Hence, the descriptive survey design will be suitable and appropriate for this study. The survey will utilize the questionnaire as the research instrument to generate primary data for this study.

3.2. Area of the Study

This research will be conducted in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA), Rivers State. ONELGA is one of the Seven Hundred and Seventy-Four (774) Local Government Areas in Nigeria. It is also one of the Twenty-Three (23) Local Government Areas in Rivers State. The headquarters of ONELGA is Omoku. ONELGA comprises of six clans, namely; Omoku, Usomini, Ndoni, Egi, Igburu and Egbema. The area is endowed with oil, gas, large water body, large land mass and rich agricultural land resources. Apart from oil and gas exploration and exploitation in this area, agriculture is still the major occupation of the inhabitants.

3.3. Population of The Study

A population is made up of all conceivable elements, subjects or observation relating to a particular phenomenon that a researcher is interested in studying or describing (Obasi, 1999; Asika, 2006). The research population is conceived mostly when one is dealing with behaviour characteristics or people’s opinion and therefore needs to select a sample (Anikpo, 2006). The

population of this study will consist of all the adult citizens of Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (ONELGA). The national census of 2006 put the population of the LGA at 284,000 domiciled in 17 wards (NPC, 2006). The population of the local government is projected above 500,000 in 2020. However, the adult population of the LGA who make direct impact on the ecosystem and cause biodiversity losses in the local government through farming, fishing, transportation, industrialization, urbanization, oil and gas exploration and exploitation, waste pollution and other related activities will form the population of the study.

3.4. Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample is precisely a part of the population, while the procedure for drawing sample from population is known as sampling (Asika, 2006). Sampling is basically used when the population, in the phrase of Gupta (1982) is ‘infinitely large’. The population of Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area is not “infinitely large”, but quite large. According to Osuala (2005), sampling is taking any portion of a population as representative of that population. The questionnaire will then be distributed on only a sample of this total population. A purposive sampling technique will be adopted to draw a total sample of One Hundred and Twenty (120) respondents from the population as sample for the study. This is a type of non-probability sampling that presupposes deliberateness in selecting the population elements to be in the sample. It actually involves hand-picking desired sample elements to ensure that such elements are considered (Anikpo, 2006; Obasi, 1999). Anikpo (2006) opines that a major variant of this technique is known as ‘Expert Opinion’ where a person is consulted specifically because he or she is supposed to be ‘the custodian of a particular type of information’. Asika (2006) also believes that in choosing sample elements the researcher is guided by what he considers typical cases which are most likely to provide him with the requisite data or information. Therefore, research instrument will be distributed among the six (6) clans through a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The clans in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area are: Omoku, Igburu, Osomini, Egi, Ndoni and Egbema. The proportionate stratified random sampling technique will help to evenly distribute the 120-sample size to these six clans. In each of the six clans, twenty (20) people will be selected randomly, making the sample size to amount to a total of One Hundred and Twenty (120) respondents.

3.5. Research Instrument

The instrument that would be adopted for the collection of data will be a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled: ‘Impact of Ecological Hazard on the Conservation of Biodiversity Questionnaire (IEHCBQ)’. The instrument will be designed using a five-point Likert type rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA = 5), Agree (S=4), Undecided

or Neutral (U/N = 3), Strongly disagree (SD = 2) and Disagree (D=1), as options to evoke unbiased responses from the respondents. The questionnaire will consist of two sections (A and B). Section 'A' will contain data on personal or demographic information of the respondents such as sex, age, occupation. While the section 'B' will contain twenty (20) items in the questionnaire which will be designed based on the specific objectives or research questions of the study. These will be answered by respondents by ticking the one most appealing to them.

3.6. Validation of the Instrument

Face and content validity methods will be used in this research. The project supervisor and measurement and evaluation expert will help in face validity. The items in the questionnaire will cross-match with both the research questions and hypotheses. Supervisor (a Lecturer in the Department of Biology Education), and expert's comments will be used to improve validity and thus establish instrument validity. Items found relevant would be retained, while irrelevant items will be removed or modified as directed by the experts.

3.7. Reliability of the Instrument

The test re-test method will be used to determine instrument reliability. 20 copies of the questionnaire will be distributed purposively and judgmentally to respondents in Ula-Ehuda community in Ahoada-East Local Government Area of Rivers State. A follow up distribution will be done after two weeks. If the same result is obtained, the instrument will then be distributed to the sample population in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State.

3.8. Method of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data will be obtained for this research. The primary data will come from a structured instrument of data collection (questionnaire). The distribution will be both proportionate and judgmental to ensure reliability of data obtained. Secondary data will be obtained from books, journal articles, newspaper publications, research instruments and publications, online (reliable) materials etc. The instrument to be used in eliciting responses from the respondents will be the questionnaire. This will help to establish the outcomes of the variables measured. Scholarly works will also be reviewed to fill the identified gaps in literature. The questionnaire will be administered personally by the researcher during field survey. Respondents will be educated on how to answer the questions. The administered instruments will be retrieved back the same day after completion by the respondents. A 100% success rate is expected and all the distributed questionnaire will be retrieved.

3.9. Method of Data Analysis

Data gotten from the respondents will be analyzed using the Mean and Standard Deviation. The research hypotheses will be tested using t-test at a 0.05 level of significance. Decision will be taken at the criteria of mean 3 for accepting an item. Item below 3 will be rejected while items with a score of 3 and above will be accepted. For the hypothesis, it will be taken at 0.05 levels of significance. If the t-cal is greater than the t-tab, the null hypothesis is rejected; if the t-cal is less than the t-tab, the null hypothesis will be accepted.

CHAPTER 4

PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This chapter discussed the findings of this work based on data presented and analysed. The data from the research instrument (questionnaire) were presented, and the findings explained. The findings were also discussed vis-à-vis other works in order to make the necessary recommendations subsequently. The sub-chapters were presentation of data, findings and discussion of findings.

4.1.1. Research Question One: What is the Nature of Biodiversity?

Table 1.

Mean responses on the nature of biodiversity.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
1.	Biodiversity is the variety of life that consists of all organisms, species and population in the environment	101	17	2	0	0	120	4.8	0.42	Accepted
2.	Biodiversity consists of plants, animals, fungi and microorganisms	87	31	1	1	0	120	4.7	0.53	Accepted
3.	Humans are integral part of the earth's biodiversity	83	33	2	2	0	120	4.6	0.60	Accepted
4.	Biodiversity is an integral part of the ecosystem in an interactive relationship with abiotic factors	67	45	6	1	1	120	4.5	0.71	Accepted
5.	Evolution of biodiversity dates back to thousands of years	56	53	9	1	1	120	4.4	0.73	Accepted

From table 1 above, it was evident that biodiversity is the variety of life that consists of all organism, species and population in the environment with the highest mean of 4.8. Biodiversity consists of plants, animals, fungi and microorganisms with a mean of 4.7. Humans are integral part of the earth's biodiversity with a mean of 4.6. on the nature of biodiversity, it is an integral part of the ecosystem in an interactive relationship with abiotic factors with a mean of 4.5. The

evolution of biodiversity dates back to thousands of years ago with a mean of 4.4. It can be deduced from Table 1 above that biodiversity is a critical and vital part of the environment and ecosystem at large which consists of plants, animals, fungi, microorganisms and most importantly, humans. It can also be deduced that biodiversity evolved years back and is in constant interaction with the abiotic components (air, sun, land, water, humidity etc.) of the environment. This interaction ensures survival and continuous living of all biological species in the ecosystem.

4.1.2. Research Question Two: What are the causes of biodiversity Loss?

Table 2.

Mean Response on the Causes of Biodiversity Loss.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	SD	Decision
6.	Biodiversity loss is triggered by harmful substances arising from dangerous and unfavourable events in the environment.	92	26	1	0	0	120	4.8	0.42	Accepted
7.	Humans are the major cause of these harmful substances released.	93	26	1	0	0	120	4.8	0.44	Accepted
8.	Biodiversity loss(es) are caused by human activities like pollution, industrialization, burning of fossil fuels, over-grazing, deforestation etc.	86	32	1	1	0	120	4.7	0.53	Accepted
9.	Natural occurrences such as earthquakes, pest invasion, flooding, epidermal invasion, storm also triggered biodiversity loss.	78	34	6	2	9	120	4.6	0.67	Accepted
10.	Biodiversity extinction is accelerated by invasive species, wildlife consumption, habitat destruction, climate change and other environmental related hazards.	56	54	8	1	1	120	4.4	0.7	Accepted

The most outstanding and significant cause of biodiversity loss is the release of harmful substances arising from dangerous and unfavourable events into the environment with a mean score of 4.8. These harmful, dangerous and unfavourable events are perpetuated by humans with a mean to score of 4.8. other causes include biodiversity loss caused by activities like

pollution, industrialization, burning of fossil fuels, over-grazing, deforestation etc. with a mean response of 4.7, natural occurrences such as earthquake, pest invasion, loss of biological diversity with a mean of 4.6 and biodiversity extinction is accelerated by invasive species, wildlife consumption, habitat destruction, climate change and other environmental related hazards. It could be inferred from the table 2 above that biodiversity loss is chiefly associated with the harmful activities of human in the environment and ecosystem at large, both to themselves and other living creatures. This is seen in Ogba-Egbema-Ndoni Local Government Area. Also, natural occurrences such as earthquake, pest invasion, apart from flooding were less significant is the loss of biodiversity as they occur rarely.

4.1.3. Research Question Three: What is the impact of Ecological Hazards on Biodiversity?

Table 3.

Mean Response on the Impact of Ecological Hazards on Biodiversity

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
11.	Ecological hazards impact negatively on biodiversity through depletion and extinction of species.	77	32	4	4	3	120	4.5	0.90	Accepted
12.	Changes of survival of biological species are the direct negative consequences of ecological hazards in the ecosystem.	59	51	8	2	0	120	4.4	0.69	Accepted
13.	Flooding, pollution, gas flaring, deforestation, unsustainable, agricultural practices and many other ecological hazards impact negatively on biodiversity.	95	22	3	0	0	120	4.8	0.48	Accepted
14.	Ecological hazards triggered the reduction in abundance and diversity of living organisms.	80	32	6	2	0	120	4.6	0.67	Accepted
15.	Disruption in communication, social order, death, loss of properties and diseases are prevailing consequences of ecological hazard that impact negatively on biodiversity.	66	40	12	2	0	120	4.4	0.74	Accepted

Data presented in table 3 above shows that biodiversity are continuously being threatened by ecological hazards released by humans into the environment. These impacts or consequences were as a result of flooding, pollution, gas flaring, deforestation, unsustainable agricultural practices among others with a mean score of 4.8. Other impacts include reduction in abundance and diversity of living organism with a mean score of 4.6; depletion and extinction of species in ONLEGA with a mean score of 4.5; changes in survival of biological species as direct negative consequences of ecological hazards in the ecosystem with a mean score of 4.4; and disruption in communication, social order, death, loss of properties and diseases are prevailing consequences of ecological hazards that impact negatively on biological species in ONELGA with a mean score of 4.4. It could be deduced that ecological hazard has never had any positive impact on biodiversity. It has always been negative. These negative impacts include depletion and extinction of species, changes in the survival of biological species, and reduction in the abundance and diversity of living organisms. Others are disruption in communication, social rder, death, loss of life and properties, outbreak of diseases on human beings and other living organisms in ONELGA.

4.1.4. Research Question Four: What ways or measures can be taken to conserve biodiversity?

Table 4.

Mean Response on the measures to be taken to conserve biodiversity.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD	TOTAL	MEAN	SD	DECISION
16.	Conservation of biodiversity should be an overall governmental strategy for species' protection.	83	34	2	1	0	120	4.7	0.56	Accepted
17.	Governments in Nigeria (especially in ONLEGA) should work to mitigate ecological hazards in the LGA to ensure biodiversity conservation.	85	32	1	1	3	120	4.6	0.73	Accepted
18.	Government, NGOs, community Based Groups and individuals should create public awareness on the dangers of biodiversity depletion and extinction on the entire ecosystem.	81	36	1	2	2	120	4.6	0.67	Accepted
19.	The general public should be educated and supported to conserve biodiversity for environmental protection and reap its benefits.	81	38	1	0	0	120	4.7	0.49	Accepted
20.	Government and stakeholders should ensure that Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) mechanism is carried out by individuals and cooperate bodies before project execution in order to maintain biodiversity conservation.	73	41	3	3	0	120	4.5	0.67	Accepted

From table 4 above, conservation of biodiversity should be an over-all governmental strategy for species' protection in ONELGA. The general public should be educated and supported to conserve biodiversity for environmental protection and reap its benefits. Respondents' mean scores of 4.7 and 4.7 respectively. Other measures to be taken to conserve biodiversity include: government in Nigeria should set to work to mitigate (reduce) ecological hazards in the local government area to ensure biodiversity conservation with a mean of 4.6. government, NGOs, community Based Groups and individuals in ONELGA should support through public awareness creation on the dangers of biodiversity depletion and extinction on the entire ecosystem with a mean of 4.6. Lastly, governments and stakeholders in ONELGA should ensure that Environmental Impact Assessment is carried out before project execution in an area. This is to maintain biological conservation with a mean of 4.5. It could be inferred that conservation of biodiversity is a collective effort, ranging from the highest (people in authority) to the middle, (NGOs and groups) and the lowest (the least individuals). All of these institutions and individuals have important roles to play in ensuring the conservation of biological species. A collaborative effort by all stakeholders concerned will reduce further depletion and extinction of biological species. The most paramount of the conservation processes is the communication and creating awareness of biodiversity, its importance and benefits, as well as the dangers of its losses to the people. This will help in designing appropriate measures or strategies for its conservation in order to sustain its numerous benefits to humanity in general.

4.2. Findings

This research observed the following as direct findings:

1. Biodiversity is the totality of all living things found on earth's ecosystem. These include plants, animals (including human beings), and other microorganisms (organisms that are not visible with the naked eyes, but can be seen with the aid of a microscope).
2. Ecological hazards are substances or occurrences that are harmful and potentially dangerous to man and his immediate environment. Ecological hazards are usually induced by man and nature.
3. Biodiversity loss results from harmful substances released by humans and natural forces into the environment.
4. The consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity are loss species, changes in survival of species, reduction in the abundance of biological species, extinction and unfavourable living conditions.
5. Biodiversity can be conserved by adhering to policies of government aimed at protecting the environment by all stakeholders concerned. Educational enlightenment, seminars, environmental awareness campaigns and empowerment of rural dwellers on

tree planting and forest preservation will also go a long way in safeguarding the environment and conserving biological species.

6. Ecological hazards have significantly altered the nature of biodiversity in ONELGA. There is also a significant impact on biodiversity depletion in the communities within the local government.

4.3. Discussion of Findings

4.3.1. Research Question One

The United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) confirmed the fact that all living organisms make up the earth's biodiversity. Respondents also affirmed that biodiversity dwells in the part of the planet earth called the biosphere. This is the layer of the planet where life exists. Living organisms that constitute biodiversity comprise of plants, animals, fungi, microorganisms as well as man. Man is considered an integral and important part of the earth's biodiversity. It is pertinent to note that these living organisms are in constant interactive relationships with their immediate environment (abiotic factor-land, air, water, sunshine etc.). Respondents agreed that living organisms have the earth as their natural habitats and make up the earth's biodiversity. This result is similar to that of Oribhabor (2016) who observed that biodiversity is the total number of different living organisms which consists of plants, animals, fungi and microbes that are found on planet earth. He further said that it is made up of the equality of genes, species and ecosystems in a region.

The United Nations Earth Summit (UNES Report, 1992) observed that biological diversity is the variability among living organisms from all sources inter-alia; terrestrial, marine and other aquatic ecosystems; and the ecological complex of which they are part of. This implies that earth's biodiversity is present and has evolved thousands of years back. It also implies that these living organisms play vital roles in the environment especially in the sustenance and maintenance of the normal functioning of the ecosystem. This research observed that ONELGA has variety of living organisms with large population. This observation of the role of biodiversity in an ecosystem is in agreement with the Nigerian Fifth National Biodiversity Report (NFNBR), which noted that biodiversity is the source of food, wide range of goods and services, raw materials and genetic materials for agriculture, medicine and health care support (under the flora family), domestic and commercial products, aesthetics and cultural ideas among others. These also constitute the values of biodiversity to the Nigerian people especially in ONELGA.

Respondents also agreed that living things were not just created or evolve recently. They agreed that evolution of biodiversity dates back millions of years ago. This research agrees with the report of the United Nations Environmental Summit (UNES, 2010) that biodiversity found on earth today consists of many millions of distinct biological species, the product of over four (4) billion years of evolution.

This research therefore agrees with other research findings that biodiversity comprises of the variety of plants, animals, fungi, microorganisms and humans. These are integral parts of the earth's biodiversity. This research also observed based on the responses of respondents that biodiversity interacts continuously with the environment. This is visible in use of land, air, water, sunlight, soil, temperature, atmosphere etc. Biodiversity relies on these abiotic factors to survive. The abiotic factors are non-living things, and affect the living organisms as well as the functioning of the ecosystem. Both the biotic and abiotic factors of an ecosystem need to be protected and conserved for optimum utilisation of biodiversity in the environment.

4.3.2. Research Question Two

Respondents agreed that causes biodiversity loss though few, were very significant. It was evident that biodiversity loss is triggered by harmful substances arising from dangerous and unfavourable events in the environment. The latter constitutes ecological hazards in the environment. Scholars in biological sciences have previously noted that ecological hazards are occurrences that are harmful and potentially dangerous to man and his immediate environment (Jay & Scott, 2011; Wright & Boorse, 2011; Mahatma, 2009; Eger & Smith, 2010). Chen (2005) observed that humans are presently facing problems like climate change, shortage in clean and accessible fresh water, ecosystem degradation, soil erosion and biodiversity loss. Respondents noted that biological species loss is happening on daily basis today. Also, biodiversity conservation has always been a big challenge. This has led to the records of millions of species that are already extinct.

Humans are the major causes of harmful substances released in the environment. Humans are the sole contributors of harmful event and substances in the ecosystem. This leads to biodiversity loss, and other negative environmental impacts. Respondents agreed that human activities constitute major reasons in the extinction of some plants and animals. They also agreed that the environment is very hot with high temperature, and no longer conducive for habitation. These were attributed to anthropogenic factors. This finding also corroborated the position canvassed by the UNEP (2010) report that the main cause of biodiversity is result of human activities and its interference with the natural environment. Human interference is also

known as anthropogenic cause of biodiversity. It is generally agreed by renowned scholars in the fields of biological conservation that humans caused most of the recorded biodiversity loss.

Majority of the respondents agreed that pollution, industrialization, over-exploitation, over-population, over-consumption, burning of fossil fuel, over-grazing, deforestation among other, led to biodiversity loss. Similarly, the UNEP (2010), and the Nigerian Fifth National Biodiversity Report (MFNBR, 2015) noted that loss of biological species came from pollution, contamination, over-exploitation, over-population, unsustainable agricultural practices and harvesting, indiscriminate use of fertilizers, gas flaring etc. Oribhabor (2016) observed that aquatic biodiversity loss was triggered by deforestation, over-exploitation of plants and animal species among others which upset the hydrological regime, sedimentary characteristics, gas flaring, industrialisation and several biotic components of the ecosystems.

Other causes of biodiversity loss emanate from the natural inherent working of the planet. When there is an instability in the inherent functioning of the planet, it gives rise to some hazards which affects biological species. Petters (1995) had opined that, while some natural disasters arise from the instability in the working of the planet; others are as a result of the mass loss of earth's materials. The outcome of these instability includes earthquake, pest invasion, storms, flooding, tornadoes etc. All of these contribute to biodiversity loss.

Nevertheless, these natural occurrences (astronomical causes) are not the sole causes of biodiversity loss in ONELGA. Astronomical causes of biodiversity losses do not happen often. This research observed that bush burning, oil exploration, deforestation and other harmful activities carried out by the indigenes of ONELGA constitute major biodiversity losses in the local government area. These activities also posed grave dangers to the well-being of the people and the environment. Policy enactments and awareness campaigns on the importance of biodiversity conservation will go a long way in the sustainable protection of the environment and conservation of biological species in the ecosystem.

4.2.3. Research Question Three

Human induced activities constitute ecological hazards in the ecosystem. Respondents agreed that flooding, pollution, gas flaring, deforestation, unsustainable agricultural practices among others constitute ecological hazards in the environment. These ecological hazards impact negatively on biological diversities. The consequences are loss, depletion and extinction of biological species. Respondents agreed that the aftermath of ecological hazard is visible in the extinction of plants and animals in the ecosystem in ONELGA. This conformed with the Nigerian Fifth National Biodiversity Report (NFNBR, 2015) which stated that the threats to

biodiversity are unsustainable agricultural practices, unsustainable harvesting, illegal logging, pollution, gas flaring, climate change, invasive species, over-grazing, bush fires among others. These threats endanger the existence of biological species in the ecosystem.

Ecological hazards also impact negatively on the survival of biological species in the environment. Hazardous substances create unfavourable conditions that are intolerable to the survival of plant and animal species in the ecosystem. Migration of biological species from one place to another in search of a favourable environment for survival happens as a result of the emission of hazardous substances in the environment. Collective migration of biological species gradually from one environment to the other leads to extinction and loss.

Ecological hazards triggered reduction in the diversity of living organisms. Respondents agreed that ecological hazards have drastically reduced the abundance of different species of plants and animals in ONELGA. This has resulted in poor yields, extinction and loss of variety in crops production. The consumption of some varieties of fruits, vegetables, crops etc. have also reduced. Indigenes eat just few varieties of food. Even aquatic habitats are not spared as fishes and aquatic lives in the aquatic ecosystem are being lost on daily basis due to the negative impacts of ecological hazards on them.

Oribhabor (2016) estimated a least 2570 faunal species. However, due to the impacts of ecological hazards, the number of aquatic species in Nigeria's faunal biodiversity is far less than estimated. Also, the rapid growth in the world's population especially in Nigeria, and particularly ONELGA, is a major challenge to biodiversity. Nigeria is a country with a rapid growing human population. Respondents agreed that growth in population has led to high reliance on natural resources. These resources are been misused, over-consumed and over-exploited.

Madu (2009) noted that population growth is a threat to the earth's biodiversity. In Nigeria, he opined that the increase in the size of Nigeria's population through a consistent growth rate puts pressure on available resources like fresh clean water and energy demands. Furthermore, he stressed that people's reliance on natural resources, and the lack of alternative to which to turn to in terms of needs, resulted in high level of use. This, he insisted, undermined their survivals. Increase in population in ONELGA has resulted in the destruction of living organisms and their habitats through unhealthy activities such as unsustainable agricultural practices, wildlife consumption on the high land, climate change among others.

4.3.4. Research Question Four

Biodiversity can be conserved through public awareness creation. Respondents agreed that the aim of biodiversity conservation is for environmental protection and the benefits derivable from it. Protecting the environment through biodiversity conservation should be an overall

governmental strategy. Humans are constantly interfering with the natural ecosystem and are ignorant of the effects of their activities. Awareness creation on the impact of unhealthy human activities that are harmful to other living organisms in the ecosystem is necessary to prevent biodiversity loss. Respondents agreed that awareness creation should be governments' responsibility. Government at all levels should collaborate with Non-governmental Organisations, biological experts, conservationists and environmentalists to protect biological species and harness their benefits.

Generally, biodiversity can be conserved if ecological hazards are controlled and mitigated. The adaptation and mitigation of ecological hazards in the environment is very paramount in the conservation of biodiversity. Biodiversity loss that are caused by anthropogenic forces can be mitigated through communication, education and public awareness. The mitigation of anthropogenic challenges is dependent on its types, causes, and consequences. Ibimilua & Ibimilua (2014) observed that curtailing man-induced desertification requires measures like irrigating farming, agro-forestry, rational grazing, prevention of illegal falling of trees, controlled use of wood as source of fuel and energy, afforestation and reforestation programmes.

In the same vein, man induced flood can be controlled through channelization and regular clearance of drainage channels, urban planning, sustainable waste management, as well as environmental sanitation. Furthermore, soil erosion control takes the form of cover cropping, contour ploughing, controlled grazing, terracing, and creation of shelter belts. Scholars agreed that disaster management is important for biodiversity conservation. This can be achieved through increased communication, education and public awareness, proper and sound environmental awareness programmes, workshops, seminars etc. These activities will help the populace to have the needed information and knowledge required for biodiversity conservation. Awareness creation will help to connect the people with the environment. It will also help to educate and inform the people on the need to take care of the environment in order to safeguard their livelihood. The significance of this lies in the protection of these natural resources, living organism and the benefits thereof for societal sustainable development.

Respondents agreed that there is the need to address and proffer solutions to the adverse effects of ecological hazards on biodiversity. The collaborative efforts of governments, non-governmental organizations, community-based organizations as well as individuals will go a long way in safeguarding the environment. These stakeholders will identify the challenges posed by ecological hazards on biological species and strategize on how best to address them. Raven et al (2010) in Ibimilua & Ibimilua (2014) agreed that addressing environmental challenges required the efforts of the governments, non-governmental organizations, community-based groups, as well as individuals in tackling them. The collaborative efforts of

international organizations, law enforcement agencies, academics, technocrats, the youths, the media as well as national and multi-national corporations are also required in the conservation of biological species in the ecosystem.

4.3.5. Research Hypotheses

The two null hypotheses were tested and the t-cal was greater than the t-tab. This means that the two hypotheses were rejected. The research therefore disagreed that:

- i. Ecological hazards have not significantly altered the nature of biodiversity in ONELGA
- ii. Ecological hazards have not impacted significantly on biodiversity depletion in ONELGA.

This research noted that ecological hazards have significantly altered the nature of biodiversity in ONELGA. Ecological hazards triggered the reduction in abundance and diversity of living organisms in the locality. Respondents agreed with this assertion with a Standard Deviation (SD score) of 0.67. Since the level of significance was 0.05; hypothesis one was rejected. Respondents also agreed that ecological hazards impacted negatively on biodiversity depletion and extinction of species in ONELGA, with a Standard Deviation (SD score) of 0.69. Similarly, since the level of significance was 0.05, hypothesis two was also rejected. What this means is that respondents agreed that ecological hazards have significantly altered the nature of biodiversity, and impacted significantly on its depletion and extinction in ONELGA.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Problem and Objective of the Study

Biological species are very important constituents of the biosphere in this plant. Their benefits cannot be overemphasized. It ranges from meeting immediate human needs as well as that of other organisms. Some of these needs biological species try to meet include clean, consistent water flows, protection from floods and storms and a stable climate. Loss of biodiversity is dangerous and its consequences are immediate. They include lack of clean water, lack of forest resources such as food or plants for medicine, less income for communities which are often already amongst the poorest on earth, fewer fish in the sea, which means less food for survival. Nigeria's biodiversity is facing a lot of threats which has led to its losses. The ones remaining are being threatened. It is therefore, pertinent, to look into the various biological species, and conserve them against possible extinctions.

In ONELGA, inhabitants are experiencing negative changes in the environment. This is as a result of ecological hazards. Ecological hazards are harmful and dangerous substances, events, states or activities introduced into the natural environment. A large number of indigenes in the local government wonder what may have gone wrong. However, few are aware of what is wrong. This is because the people in these rural areas are not aware or are ignorant of the impact of their activities on the environment. Some also wonder why certain crops that are of great health importance are not doing well in the region again; unlike years back. They also wonder why some certain plants and aquatic lives cannot be seen again. The curiosity is as a result of ignorance of the negative impacts of their activities on them, other living things and the environment at large. Therefore, it is important to examine the impacts of ecological hazards on biodiversity, and ways to conserve biodiversity from further loss and extinction.

Conclusively, the research seeks to critically examine the nature, causes, impacts and challenges of ecological hazards on biological species conservation in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area; and also to proffer solutions for its mitigation and adaptation strategies.

5.2. Procedure Used.

The main purpose of this research is to ascertain the impact of ecological hazards on biodiversity conservation in ONLEGA of Rivers State. Descriptive survey design was used in carrying out the study. As a guide, four (4) research questions were formulated. The sample of this study was One-Hundred and Twenty (120) respondents, all consisting of adults selected randomly from the six (6) clans in ONLEGA. The research instrument used for data collection was a twenty (20) item questionnaire. This was designed using a five-point Likert rating scale. The data gathered was analysed using the mean and standard deviation method. While the hypothesis was tested using the t-test at a 0.05 level of significance. In the course of carrying out this research, a number of literatures that were related to this study were reviewed.

5.3. Major Findings

From the data analysed, the following were the major findings.

1. Biodiversity is the variety of life that consist of all living organisms, species and population in the environment. It consists of plants, animals, fungi and microorganisms. Also, it recognized humans as an integral part of the earth's biodiversity.
2. Biodiversity is facing great threats. Its loss is as a result of harmful substances arising from dangerous and unfavourable events in the environment majorly released by human activities.
3. Ecological hazards are chiefly brought about by human activities as well as natural events. However, human-induced changes are prevalent. Some of which include pollution, flaring of petroleum gases, deforestation, unsustainable agricultural practices, over-grazing, over-population, over-consumption, over-exploitation, etc.
4. Changes in survival of species, depletion, extinction, reduction in the abundance of biological species are all direct consequences of ecological hazards on biodiversity. Furthermore, disruption in communication and social order, death, loss of properties, diseases among others, are indirect prevailing consequences of ecological hazards.
5. Biodiversity conservation is majorly dependent on the promulgation of policies and programmes, creation of awareness to the general public concerning the benefits of biodiversity, and dangers of biodiversity depletion and extinction on the entire ecosystem. This should be a collective effort of the government, NGOs, community-based groups as well as individuals.
6. Ecological hazards have significantly altered the nature of biodiversity, and impacted significantly on its depletion and extinction in ONLEGA.

5.4. Implications of the Findings.

From the analysis carried out, it was observed that ecological hazards have negative impacts on biodiversity known by individuals and groups. It also showed that about 80% of the earth's biodiversity is being depleted and under the threat of extinction. This implies that there is a need to take drastic measures towards mitigating the impact of ecological hazards on biodiversity. This will be achieved through increase in the awareness level of individual adults on the impact of their daily collective activities on other living organisms such as plants, animals (both terrestrial and aquatic and arboreal) and the immediate environment too.

Gas flaring is the introduction of chemical compounds/substances into the air, and this makes air uncondusive. Therefore, human should be educated on their activities on both the living and non-living components of the environment. The ability of an individual to effectively curtail and monitor his activities in order to reduce the actions of endangering the lives of other organisms and the conservation of the environment is determined by the quality of information about biodiversity and the tools needed to ensure reduction of harmful practices. It is on the basis of the high level of information and knowledge, and the tools required by people that they can make certain vital changes towards the conservation of biodiversity. The role of awareness creation is a collective responsibility of the government, NGOs, Community-Based Groups as well as individuals. However, environmental specialists known as environmentalists and biological experts should take up the lead towards advocating for the protection of the biosphere from misuse from human activity through such measures as ecosystem protection, waste reduction and pollution prevention and to safeguard livelihood.

The result of this research showed that respondents in this study area are witnessing the challenges and impacts of ecological hazards which manifest in climate changes, increase in flooding, changes in rainfall intensity and distribution, drought, increase in temperature, high incidence of pests and diseases, declining soil fertility and decrease in crop yields, biodiversity loss, fresh water degradation, stratospheric ozone layer depletion, soil erosion and reduction in farm productivity. This implies that biodiversity is highly vulnerable and is threatened by the effects of ecological hazards. If quick actions are not taken towards the mitigation of these hazards, biodiversity will be lost and other constituent, function and composition of the ecosystem will be affected and frustrated too. Also, the benefits of biodiversity will not be enjoyed, thereby worsening the degree of survival of all living organisms.

5.5. Conclusion

Environmental hazards impinge negatively on humans, the environment and other living organisms in the environment. The consequences on the human livelihoods, other living organisms and the environment are enormous. These consequences include biodiversity loss, environmental degradation, stratospheric ozone layer depletion, habitat destruction, flooding, soil erosion etc. Ecological conservation primarily focused on the protection of biodiversity from future extinction, reduce threats, safeguard livelihoods of living organisms among others. The mitigation of anthropogenic causes is aimed at reducing the activities of humans that interfere with the natural ecosystem and reduce the impacts of interference on the conservation of the ecosystem. Nigeria as a developing country, should aim at enlightening the populace, educating individuals and organizations, creating awareness, incorporating relevant skills and knowledge, through trained and informed environmentalists and biological experts especially in the rural areas and implementing policies and enforcing policy decisions and agreements.

5.6. Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are presented for consideration by relevant stakeholders in biodiversity conservation:

1. Citizens should not underestimate the role of environmentalists and biological experts. Their roles should be properly communicated to people in the region so that they can welcome the opportunity of having them.
2. Government policies should address the need to support the training of environmental agents. This is to ensure that they are able to give relevant information about the environment. They should be equipped with all the necessary information and skills to disseminate information in a simple manner that individual will comprehend.
3. Agreements related to biodiversity conservation should be implemented. Conservation of Biological Species (CBS) whose goal is to conserve biological species, make sustainable use of its components and share fairly and equitably the benefits arising from its genetic resources should be sustained.
4. Government, NGOs and Community Based Groups should make efforts towards mitigating ecological hazards and increasing biodiversity conservation.
5. There is need for Government, NGOs, community Based Groups, Environmentalists and Biological Experts to utilize technological resources especially media platforms such as television, radio, internet, newspapers and billboards etc. in showcasing the dangers of ecological hazards, create awareness on biodiversity and communicate effective measures to be taken in protecting biological species.

5.7. Limitations of the Study

Financial constraints, inadequate time allotment and lack of access to confidential documents were the major limitations of this research. Self-funded researches faced financial challenges that undermined smooth completion of the research endeavours. This was applicable to this research. Efforts of relatives and friends helped in the completion of this work. Also, the time allocation by the college for the research endeavour was too short. The coronavirus pandemic disrupted academic activities and a very limited time was made available for the research. Furthermore, confidential documents that would have aided the research were not made available from those concerned. The research also noted the non-availability of literature on ecological hazards and biodiversity in ONELGA. Efforts were made to ensure that address the issue of lack of literature with the use of primary source of data collection (questionnaire), and field survey of selected communities in ONELGA.

5.8. Suggestions for Further Studies.

The scope of the study was limited to ONELGA. This study can be carried out in Rivers state and other parts of the country. The following topics can be researched on:

1. Biodiversity and its benefits in Rivers State.
2. Conservation of Biodiversity in Rivers State: Problems and Prospects.
3. Biodiversity Multilateral Agreements: A Vehicle to Biodiversity Conservation in Nigeria.

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